

HEALTH STATUS AND HEALTH CARE EXPENDITURE IN INDIA –AN ANALYSIS WITH A FOCUS ON KERALA STATE

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Abstract:

Health is a multi-dimensional phenomenon. It is both an end and means of development strategy. The relationship between health and development is mutually reinforcing: while health contributes to economic development, economic development, in turn, tends to improve the health status of the population in a country. Health is also an important entitlement that enhances “capabilities” of the poor people leading to increase in “commodities” and further improvement in health status. As investment on health increases, the productive capacity and the level of income tends to rise and to that extent, it contributes to a decline in the incidence of poverty. With rapid improvement in health, particularly of the poor, “vicious circle” of poverty can be converted into “virtuous circle” of prosperity. Acknowledging this significance, Economics of Health is assigned as a special branch of study.

The role of health in the formation of human capital is vital. Unless a population is healthy enough to work and earn, the society will remain backward. Only strong and healthy people can struggle and survive and can take the nation forward. Thus, health is a form of human capital as well as an input to produce other forms of human capital. Being unhealthy depresses the ability to work and the productivity of the person. This implies that worse health implies lower income. When people get richer, they invest more in their own health. The correlation between health and income might be one of circular and cumulative causation: health affects income and income affects health. Considering the relevance of maintaining good health for the entire population all over the world, April 7th is celebrated as World Health Day by the UN declaration.

Introduction

The constitution of World Health Organization (WHO) states “enjoyment of the highest standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction of race, religion and political belief, economic and social condition”. According to the Right to Health in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, “Every one has the right to a standard of living, adequate for the well being of himself and his family”. At this juncture, it is appropriate to quote the opinion of the general mass. In a survey conducted by the United Nations in September 2000, respondents from around the world overwhelmingly ranked health as their “number one” desire. (Millennium poll, United Nations, New York, 2000). It is a coincidence that “good wishes” cards for the New year from anywhere in the world normally include health as one of the top wishes. This seems to be a wide consensus among people throughout the world that health is their primary asset.

The costs of bad health

For an average person, falling sick for any length of time seriously endangers the economic situation and well-being of both the individual and their family in the short and long term because

1. Bad health will have a severe impact on the individual’s level of income due to treatment costs and reduced work of the sick.

2. It will decrease the capacity of the individual and other family members to acquire suitable education. Both the sick and the family members looking after them miss opportunities for education and training in the formal or informal sector. It will also affect the family's productive opportunities as other members of the family will be called upon to assist the sick.
3. If ill health persists, the family may fall into absolute poverty due to loss of income and the "catastrophic payments" needed to regain health.
4. Disease for one member of the family means an increase in malnutrition of all family members due to reduced consumption. Malnutrition increases the risk of illness leading to further loss of work resulting less family revenue.
5. An already poor housing situation with low productivity level further deteriorates due to illness in the long run. Access to health care services, safe drinking water and social services, in general, may become even more precarious as a result of lower revenue.
6. The sale of assets for survival may force the family to move to a more degraded environment. Its overall impact is to reinforce the powerlessness of the family members, putting at risk the survival of the family itself.
7. Finally, it will adversely affect the psychological well-being of the sick and his family members.

It is clearly acknowledged that bad health causes irrecoverable losses in the production of the economy due to the absence or reduction of work resulting from the illness of the sick and their relatives who may be called upon to assist them. A less trained labour force will be denied of education and training opportunities due to sickness. Further more, there is the absorption of resources for treating illnesses (both human and financial) that could otherwise be invested in alternative activities. The so-called externalities include lower productivity, lower profitability of enterprises, lower labour force turnover and disruption in the national budget in general. In the long run, bad health will endanger the survival of the less competitive enterprises as well as the country's ability to attract foreign investments and the possibility of getting foreign market. Employment opportunities in the economy become lower by increasing the quantum of unemployed. Another fatal externality operates in the form of a higher rate of disease transmission over a wider range of the community.

Benefits of better health

Better health will boost the individual's level of income due to lower or absence of treatment costs, increased and regular revenue because of better work opportunities and longer life expectancy. It enhances the individual's capacity to acquire education as well as the family's productive opportunities by freeing the members who would otherwise have been called upon to care for the sick. Another merit is that the psychological well-being of both the individual and the family could be substantially enhanced. The benefits of good health will be even greater for the absolute poor, as they may transform the vicious circle of poverty into a virtuous circle, with better nutrition, lower risks of unemployment or underemployment, better housing, better use of training opportunities, higher productivity and better control over the individual's life situation and that of the family. Various studies indicate that investment in health is the best form of human investment which are yielding the highest rates of return compared to other public investments.

Determinants of health

The World Health Organization (WHO) defined health as “a state of complete physical, mental and social well being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. Thus, the health status of a community depends on its socio-economic, environmental and biological factors. As health is a multi- dimensional and multi-casual variable, it depends on various factors such as income of the person, pattern of educational attainment, density of population, age structure, public investment in health care, medical facilities, geographical factors such as location and climate of a country, food, housing, basic sanitation, measures to control communicable diseases, etc.

Many factors simultaneously affect the health of individuals and communities. The determinants of health include:

1. **Income and social status:** - Higher income and social status are linked to better health. The greater the gap between the richest and poorest people, the greater the differences in health.
2. **Education:** –Better education levels are linked with good health, less stress and higher self-confidence.
3. **Physical environment:** –Safe water and clean air, healthy working environment, neat and clean houses, pollution free communities and roads contribute to good health.
4. **Social support networks:** –Greater support from families, friends and communities are linked to better health. Culture, customs and traditions and the beliefs of the family and community also affect health.
5. **Genetics:**- Inheritance plays an important role in determining lifespan, healthiness and the likelihood of developing certain illnesses. Personal behaviour and coping skills like balanced eating, keeping active, smoking and drinking habit and the mode of facing life’s stresses and challenges affect health.
6. **Health services:** - Access and use of health services that prevent and treat disease influences health.
7. **Gender:** - Men and women suffer from different types of diseases at different ages.

Trends and pattern of health expenditure in India

The health care system in India is pre-dominantly catered to by the public sector, private sector and a minuscule contribution through external flows. Public health care system includes health expenditure by the Centre, States and local bodies. Within the gamut of public health spending, a significant contribution has been made by the state governments.

Private health expenditure in India includes out of pocket expenditure, health insurance and expenditure towards health by firms and NGOs. Among all these components, out of pocket expenditure has the single largest share in the total health expenditure of the country.

As per the latest National Health Accounts Report 2010, out of the total health expenditure, the share of private sector was the highest at 71.62 percent, 26.70 percent by public sector and 1.68 percent by external flows.

Figure 1 Health expenditure in India

Source: National Health Accounts Report 2010, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.

Total health expenditure as percentage of GDP

Total health expenditure as percentage of GDP in India is comparatively low. It had increased from 4.27 in 2000 to 4.50 in 2004. But since 2004, it has been declining to 4.25 in 2005, 4.03 in 2006, 3.88 in 2007, 3.93 in 2008, 3.95 in 2009, 3.75 in 2010 and 3.87 in 2011. Compared to India, many Asian countries had a relatively higher percentage; for example, China (4.3%), Nepal (6.0%), Mali (5.6%) and Bhutan (5.5%).

Figure 2 Health expenditure as percentage of GDP

Source: National Health Account database, World Health Organisation.

Health expenditure as percentage of GDP is much higher in the developed countries compared to developing countries (World Health Statistics, 2011). The share of GDP spent on health in USA is 15.2 percent, France (11.2%), Germany (10.5%), U.K (8.7%), Japan (8.3%) while in India it is only 3.87 percent. This reveals that

for highly advanced countries, expenditure on health as percentage of GDP is very high as they can afford to spend a sizeable amount for maintaining the health of their citizens. These countries account for less than 20 percent of the world’s population but were responsible for almost 90 percent of the world’s health spending. Therefore the remaining 80 percent of world’s population spend only 10 percent of the total world expenditure on health. This includes people in the Asia- Pacific as well as African and Latin American countries. Africa accounts for about 25 percent of the global burden of disease but only about 2 percent of global health spending (WHO Report 2003).

Public and private health expenditure as percentage of total health expenditure

Total health expenditure consists of public and private expenditure on health. Public expenditure on health as percentage of total health expenditure shows a decreasing trend during the period of 2000 to 2004, that is from 25.97 percent in 2000 to 20.93 percent in 2004. Since 2005, it has been increasing gradually and reached at 31 percent in 2011. It is lower than many Asian countries like China (47.3%), Malaysia (44.1%), Sri Lanka (43.7%), Nepal (37.7%) and Thailand (74.3%).

Compared to developed and many developing countries, India’s private expenditure on health is very high. While the world average is 38.4 percent, private expenditure on health in India is 69 percent. It is seen that advanced countries had a lesser proportion of private expenditure on health such as UK (17.4%), Japan (18%), Austria (20.9%), France (21.4%), Italy (23.7%), Canada (30.5%), etc (National Health Account database, World Health Organisation).

Public health expenditure as percentage of government expenditure

Public health expenditure as percentage of government expenditure has declined significantly from 7.39 in 2000 to 5.89 in 2003. However, it has reached at 8.05 percent in 2011. According to the latest health statistics published by WHO (2011), Government spending on health per person is just \$ 122 per annum in India while it is \$ 7,164 in America. Even China, having bigger share of population than India, spend \$ 265 per person. This indicates the lesser consideration for the maintenance and protection of health in our country.

Figure 3 Public health expenditure as percentage of government expenditure

Source: National Health Account database, World Health Organisation

Out of pocket health expenditure as percentage of total expenditure on health

Out of pocket (OOP) payments are the principal source of health care finance in most Asian countries and India is not an exception. It constitutes more than two third of total health expenditure in India. In 2000, 67.97 percent of total health expenditure is out of pocket payments and it is increased to 71.57 in 2004. Since then, it has been decreasing gradually and reached at 59.36 percent in 2011 (National Health Account database, World Health Organisation).

In India, not only the private health care spending is much higher than government spending in comparison to what is observed in developed and many developing countries, but also within the private health spending, the share of out of pocket (OOP) health spending is much higher. This reveals that Indians had to bear real burden for their health expenditure. The share of OOP expenditure in total expenditure on health is 74.74 percent for India (World Health Statistics, WHO, 2011). It is very high compared to the developed countries such as USA (24.4%), France (34.6%), Canada (50.9%), and Germany (53.9%) and many developing countries such as Indonesia (70.3%), Nepal (72.4%) and Malaysia (73.2%).

Distribution of health expenditure by public and private sector in major states

The proportional distribution of health expenditure between public and private sector in different states show wide variation with a major portion incurred in private sector.

As shown in table 1, share of public health expenditure is highest in Nagaland (78%) while it is 9.73 percent in Kerala. Share of public spending is comparatively very higher in Mizoram (76.50%), Sikkim (71.80%), etc. States having higher share of private expenditure on health are Kerala (90.27%), UP (86.88%), West Bengal (86.28%), Maharashtra (83.19%), Tamil Nadu (82.28%), Punjab (81.82%), etc.

Table 1 Distribution of health expenditure by Public and Private sector in major states

States	Share of public percent)	(in	Share of Private	(in percent)
Andhra Pradesh	17.99		82.01	
Arunachal Pradesh	57.83		42.17	
Assam	20.89		79.11	
Bihar	18.15		81.85	
Gujarat	20.81		79.19	
Haryana	18.83		81.17	
Himachal Pradesh	41.70		58.30	
Jammu and Kashmir	51.17		48.83	
Jharkhand	31.02		68.98	
Karnataka	28.08		71.92	
Kerala	9.73		90.27	
Madhya Pradesh	18.36		81.64	
Maharashtra	16.81		83.19	
Goa	37.46		62.54	

Manipur	43.71	56.29
Meghalaya	48.12	51.88
Mizoram	76.53	23.47
Nagaland	78.00	22.00
Orissa	20.28	79.72
Punjab	18.18	81.82
Rajasthan	24.45	75.55
Sikkim	71.78	28.22
Tamil Nadu	17.72	82.28
Tripura	22.06	77.94
Uttar Pradesh	13.12	86.88
West Bengal	13.72	86.28
All India	20.13	79.87

Source: National Health Profile 2009, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare.

Investment on health over the plan period

Health expenditure over the planning period has increased in India. In the first plan, investment for health was Rs.65.3 crore, which was 3.4 percent of total investment. In the eleventh five year plan, health investment has increased to as much as 6.05 percent of the total investment indicating increased priority for health sector.

Table 2 Investment over the plan period (rupees in crore). Figure in brackets shows the percentage

Plan	Plan period	Total plan investment outlay	Total health investment
First	1951-56	1960	65.3 (3.4)
Second	1956-61	4672	145.8 (3.1)
Third	1961-66	8576.5	250.8 (2.9)
Fourth	1969-74	15778.8	613.5 (3.2)
Fifth	1974-79	39426.2	1252.6 (3.1)
Sixth	1980-85	109291.7	3412 (3.1)
Seventh	1985-90	218729.6	6809.4 (3.1)
Eighth	1992-97	434100	14102.2 (3.2)
Ninth	1997-02	859200	35204.95 (4.09)
Tenth	2002-07	1484131	58920.3 (3.97)
Eleventh	2007-12	2156571	140135 (6.05)

Source: Planning Commission Reports 1951-56 to 2007-12.

Health status in Kerala

The population of Kerala is uniformly scattered throughout the state and is fairly well advanced in its demographic transition. The rapidly declining growth rate of population, highest mean age at marriage, high level of awareness and adoption of family planning methods, moderate decline in the mortality rate, etc are commendable

achievements in health standards which are similar to developed countries. Low birth and death rate along with higher female life expectancy, low infant mortality with negligible gap between rural and urban areas are the special characteristics of Kerala. A person at birth is expected to live for 74 years in Kerala, while it is 63 years for all-India. Kerala, with an IMR of 13, is the best performing state in the country. The major factors contributing to such a unique situation are a wide network of health infrastructure, better man power and other social factors like women’s education, general health awareness and clean health habits of the people. A comparison of the basic health indicators of Kerala and India are given in table 3.

Death rate has slightly increased in Kerala during 2012 ie, from 6.4 in 2007 to 7 per thousand population. Spreading of communicable diseases and life style diseases are major factors for this. MMR has declined considerably from 110 per lakh live birth during 10th Plan to 81 during 11th Plan.

Table 3 Basic Health Indicators in Kerala and India during 2007 & 2012

Health Indicators	Kerala		India		
	2007	2012	2007	2012	
Birth rate (‘000 population)	15	14.8	23.8	22.1	
Death rate (‘000 population)	6.4	7	7.6	7.2	
Infant mortality rate (‘000 population)	14	13	58	47	
Child mortality rate 0-4 years (‘000 population)	3	2	17	15	
Maternal mortality rate (per lakh live birth)	110	81	300	212	
Total fertility rate (children per woman)	1.7	1.7	2.9	2.6	
Couple protection rate (in percent)	72.1	62.3	52	52	
Life at birth	Male	70.9	71.4	61.8	62.6
		76	76.3	63.5	64.2
	Female	73.45	74	62.7	63

Source: Directorate of Health Services, various issues.

Major Health Problems in Kerala

Though Kerala has registered a significant improvement in key health care indicators, the health situation in the state reflects a paradox. It is a paradox of high morbidity rate and low mortality rate. Incidence of morbidity is higher in Kerala than India as a whole and it is 25.15 percent for Kerala as against 9.11 percent for all India.

Table 4 Incidence of morbidity- Kerala and All- India

Gender	All Kerala			All India		
	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total
Male	24.28	23.56	24.09	8.36	9.11	8.56
Female	26.66	24.51	26.10	9.30	10.86	9.69
Total	25.53	24.06	25.15	8.82	9.95	9.11

Source: Tabulated from NSS Unit Record Data (60th Round).

Table 5 Incidence of life style diseases (chronic) per lakh population

Name of diseases	India	Kerala
Hypertension	589	1433
Diabetes	221	980
Heart diseases	385	914
Mental diseases	132	283

Source: Economic Review, State Planning Board, Thiruvananthapuram

Budgetary allocation on health sector in Kerala

Public investment on health sector in Kerala is steadily diminishing especially in the liberalized context of the economy. Table 6 reveals the declining trend in investment on medical and public health in Kerala particularly after 1991.

Table 6 Allocation in state budget for health and family welfare

Year	Amount of rupees in lakhs	Percentage of health expenditure in the state budget
1960-61	541	8.24
1965-66	981	8.74
1975-76	4627	7.71
1980-81	7879	6.82
1985-86	12681	6.56
1990-91	27850	4.18
2003-04	106200	4.10
2004-05	115376	3.65
2005-06	116574	3.73
2006-07	133417	4.10
2007-08	144832	3.65
2008-09	180256	3.73
2009-10	200815	3.80
2010-11	256960	4.00
2011-12	328957	4.01

Source: State government budget in various years.

The vital issue of the health sector in Kerala is the problem of increased morbidity reported due to the spread of communicable diseases such as Dengue, AIDs, Malaria, Leptospirosis, Hepatitis, Chikungunya, etc. During 2012, Kerala has reported maximum number of dengue cases (3033) and 12 cases of death. Water supply mismanagement, gaps in public health infrastructure, increased inter-state mobility of population and poor infrastructure to monitor mosquito breeding were some of the reasons for the spread of communicable diseases. Wide spread pollution due to the higher use of fossil fuel, vehicle transportation, increasing sedentary habits particularly in the IT field, higher use of tobacco and intoxicated liquors even among youngsters, etc. are the basic reasons for increased respiratory infectious diseases. During the rainy season, communicable diseases dominate the rural and urban slums of the state. Adverse impact of ineffective sewage and drainage systems as well as improper waste management aggravate the spread of communicable diseases.

Conclusion

The typical feature of the post reform health scenario of Kerala is the perceptible change in public expenditure on health care, that is, a shift occurred from health care to medical care. Social sector expenditure declined considerably during this period and a major portion of public expenditure on health was directed for the disbursement of salaries.

The health scenario in Kerala was hunky during the pre-liberalization days. However, during the post-liberalization period, many a problem cropped up in the health care system and health indicators gradually started showing an unfavorable trend in many cases and getting worse than the average of all India indicators over time. The morbidity rate is now at an all time high, malnutrition and under nutrition is alarming, various types of chronic diseases are predominant, calorie intake is going down and infant mortality has started to rise. In the meantime, the state expenditure has been declining and government owned institutions stand outdated due to lack of modern health infrastructure and shortage of properly skilled manpower. The globalization has reduced the health sector to shambles and prepared the stage for a victory of the private sector.

The failure of government facilities to meet demand led to the mushrooming of the private sector and escalation in private health care expenditure. Besides, more emphasis was laid on curative medicine and less on preventive medicine. Large increase in private health care expenditure, privatization of medical education, reduction in public spending, neglect of PHCs, etc had converted health care into market driven, profit driven enterprises. This has led to the 'commercialization and the commodification' of health care. Health is no more seen as a right but as a commodity to be purchased by money.

The analysis of data related to health indicators point out the need for greater attention to improve and sustain the health status of the people of Kerala. There is acute shortage of investment in medical and public health, better infrastructural facilities such as good drinking water, sanitation and sewage system leading to inefficient environmental facilities.

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